

**LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF MOTION VERBS IN THE
ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND THEIR COMPARISON WITH THE UZBEK
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: This article deals with the lexical and semantic issues of verbs of motion in English and Uzbek. At the same time, the lexica-semantic group of verbs of motion in English and Uzbek languages, denoting the main types of movement of an animated subject in space, is subjected to analysis.

Keywords: lexical and semantic verbs, verbs of motion, verbs of the English language, verbs of the Uzbek language.

The current language situation in Uzbekistan and the ongoing language policy provide not only full knowledge of the Uzbek language, which has the status of the state language, but also the formation and development of a harmonious two and three languages, an integral component of which is English [1]. The realities of modern life, the development of international relations require scientifically based educational and methodological equipment for the process of teaching foreign languages.

Among the topical problems considered by domestic and foreign lexicologists, the problem of the functioning of lexico-semantic groups of verbs, which are one of the manifestations of the systemic nature of the vocabulary of the language, stands out.

A large number of works of domestic and foreign linguists are devoted to the verbs of motion [2, 3]. English, Russian verbs of motion were studied from the point of view of their lexical meaning, the attention of researchers was drawn to the semantic features of this group of verbs, including in the comparative aspect, the features of the functioning of the verbs of motion in the text were considered. Russian and foreign researchers are guided by different principles in the selection of lexical material, use

different approaches to describing the movement process and its indicators. Until now, there is no stability in terminology, there is no consensus on the principles of singling out and delimiting the verbs of this group, its quantitative composition is established in different ways. In addition, there are no special works devoted to a comparative analysis of the semantic structure of English and Uzbek verbs of motion and its changes in the process of functioning in speech (context). This determines the relevance of this study.

The lexico-semantic group of verbs of motion is one of the most ancient and striking verb groups [4, 5]. Interest in the study of this group of verbs is due to the fact that in the world around us and nature there is no process more common than movement. Various forms of movement find the most specialized expression in the lexico-semantic group of movement verbs.

The relevance of this direction is determined from a theoretical point of view by the fact that it fills the existing gap in the Anglo-Uzbek linguistics, since there are no special works devoted to a comparative analysis of the semantic structure of English and Uzbek verbs of motion and its changes in the process of functioning in speech (context), and from a practical point of view, by the fact that its material can serve as a linguistic basis for teaching the use of English and Uzbek verbs of motion in an Uzbek audience.

To solve these problems, you can use component analysis, which establishes the semantic structure of English verbs of motion. And also with a comparative analysis of semantic processes in the semantic structure of verbs, an integrated approach can be used, including a descriptive method, for example, observation techniques, material grouping and classification, elements of oppositional and contextual analysis.

The methodology in our research is based on the main provisions of the theory of speech activity, set out in the works of L.V. Shcherby, M.M. Bakhtin, the theory of semantic fields V.P. Abramov, Yu.D. Apresyan, B.Yu. Gorodetsky, G. Ipsen, E. Coseriou, V. Portzig, Yu.S. Stepanov, as well as on numerous studies in the field of

studying the semantic groupings of verbs, varieties of the course of action in the English language A.Kh. Vostokov, A.A. Potebnya, F.F. Fortunatov, A.A. Shakhmatov, V.V. Vinogradov. On the basis of these scientific achievements, an attempt was made to determine the semantic groupings and semantic fields of verbs of motion in languages with different systems, highlighting the core and periphery.

A prerequisite for the lexico-semantic description of the verbs of motion in any language is the establishment of a list of these verbs according to various lexicographic sources of the English and Uzbek languages [6-8]. Since it is assumed that the verbs of motion of any language form a semantic field or a lexico-semantic system built on the presence of integral features in all these verbs, this gives reason to consider the verbs of motion we are studying as a synonymous series.

The practical material collected for analysis shows that, unlike the Uzbek language, it is almost impossible to give a detailed description of the lexical and semantic properties of all verbs of motion in English, since, firstly, the list of verbs of motion remains open anyway; secondly, the function of verbs of motion can be performed not only by generally recognized verbs of motion, but by many verbs that form the sphere of verbs of movement, change of state.

It is clear that the most frequent verbs must belong to the core of the verbs of the semantic field of motion, while the less frequent and especially rare verbs belong to the periphery of this field. Of course, the criterion of frequency may not always be decisive, since there are sublanguages, functional styles that prefer to use one rather than another verb of movement (the language of science, philosophy, journalism, fiction, etc.).

In our opinion, the most frequent verbs of motion belong to the core of the semantic field of verbs of motion, and the less frequent, especially rare, belong to the periphery. To determine the frequency, we used a statistical method for studying the works of English-speaking authors and their translations into Uzbek. From two sources of examples in English and Uzbek (Agatha Christie - Selected stories. - M., 1985 and their translations into Uzbek), 5400 verbs of motion in English and Uzbek were

extracted by continuous sampling, belonging to the core of the semantic field of verbs of motion in the studied languages of different systems.

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